

Synthesis and Structure Determination of 6-Chloro-1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-*b*]pyrido[2,3-*d*] and [3,2-*d*]pyridazines

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5,8-Dichloropyrido[2,3-*d*]pyridazine when treated with hydrazine hydrate gave a mixture of 5-chloro-8-hydrazino- and 8-chloro-5-hydrazinopyrido[2,3-*d*]pyridazines which when allowed to react with formic acid gave 6-chloro-1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-*b*]pyrido[2,3-*d*] and [3,2-*d*]pyridazines.

CONDENSED triazoles possess a variety of pharmacological activities¹. In continuation of our work on pyridopyridazine², we were interested in the synthesis of triazolopyridopyridazines. The synthesis of 1,2,4-triazolo systems has been reported by a number of workers³. In many instances formic acid has been used for the cyclisation of the hydrazino compounds to the corresponding triazoles.

Results and Discussion

6,7-Dihydropyrido[2,3-*d*]pyridazine-5,8-dione (1) when treated with phosphorous oxychloride under nitrogen gave 5,8-dichloropyrido[2,3-*d*]pyridazine (2). The structure of 2 was confirmed by its elemental analysis, ir spectrum which showed the disappearance of the absorption due to NH and C=O, and pmr spectrum which showed the AMX system of the three protons of the pyridine ring. Treatment of 2 with hydrazine hydrate in refluxing dioxane, yielded two compounds having isomeric structures 5-chloro-8-hydrazinopyrido[2,3-*d*]pyridazine (3) and 8-chloro-5-hydrazinopyrido[2,3-*d*]pyridazine (4) rather than the dihydrazino derivative. The formations of 3 and 4 which could not be separated by means of either crystallisation or column chromatography were proved when the mixture was allowed to react with formic acid. The reaction was followed by tlc at different time intervals which indicated the formation of two different products in ~ 1 h and was completed after 12 h. By means of column chromatography, 6-chloro-1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-*b*]pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyridazine (5; eluded first) and 6-chloro-1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-*b*]pyrido[3,2-*d*]pyridazine (6; major product) were separated. An unambiguous proof for the structures of 5 and 6 have been provided by the nmr spectra (DMSO) and compared with that of 1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-*b*]pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrida-

zine² of related structure. The chemical shift for H_a in 5 appeared more downfield than H_c in 6 (δ 9.03 and 8.73). This may be attributed to the $-I$ effect of chlorine atom on H_c in 5 and the anisotropic shielding effect of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ in 6.

The formation of 6 as the major product could be explained due to nucleophilic displacement of the chlorine atom in the 5-position in 2, in comparison with the chlorine in the 8-position due to the formation of the stabilised resonating structure 7.

Experimental

All melting points were recorded on a Büchi melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. ^1H nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian T60, spectrometer, infrared spectra (KBr) on a Acculab. 1, Beckman spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a monofocussing Varian CH-5 spectrometer.

5,8-Dichloropyrido[2,3-d]pyridazine (2) : 6,7-Dihydropyrido[2,3-d]pyridazine-5,8-dione (1 ; 350 mg, 2.1 mmol) was treated with pyridine (166 mg, 2.1 mmol) and phosphorous oxychloride (8 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h at 110° under nitrogen. After cooling the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water (100 ml) and extracted as soon as possible with chloroform (100 ml). The organic layer was separated, washed with water, 1N sodium hydroxide and finally with water. The extracted chloroform was dried over sodium sulphate and evaporated under reduced pressure. The oily residue obtained was purified using silica gel column (15 cm $\times$ 2.5 dia.) and ether as an eluent to give 2 (320 mg, 74.5%), m.p. $162-63^\circ$ (Found : N, 21.30. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4$ (200) calcd. for : N, 21.00%); ν_{max} 3 080 (CH), 1 590, 1 555, 1 530, 1 380, 1 305, 1 240 and 1 010 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 8.06 (1H, dd, H_b), 8.70 (1H, dd, H_c), 9.45 (1H, dd, H_a).

5-Chloro-8-hydrazino- and 8-chloro-5-hydrazino-pyrido[2,3-d]pyridazines (3 and 4) : A mixture of 2 (280 mg, 1.4 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (5 ml, 100 mmol) in dioxane (20 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid formed was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to give 3 and 4 (220 mg, 80%). All attempts to separate 3 from 4 by fractional crystallisation or by using tlc with different eluent ratios were unsuccessful, (Found : C, 42.71; H, 3.25; N, 36.02. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{ClN}_5$ (195.6) calcd. for : C, 42.95; H, 3.09; N, 35.81; ν_{max} 3 280-3 420 (NH), 1 620, 1 590, 1 560, 1 505 and 1 390 cm^{-1}).

6-Chloro-1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-b]pyrido[2,3-d]pyridazine (5) and 6-chloro-1,2,4-triazolo[4,3-b]pyrido[3,2-d]pyridazine (6) : A solution of 3 and 4 (200 mg,

1.02 mmol) in excess formic acid (30 ml) was warmed on an oil-bath at $45-50^\circ$ for 12 h. The solution was cooled and poured into ice-water mixture. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, then with water and dried. Using silica gel column (30 cm $\times$ 2.5 cm dia.) and ether-petroleum ether (5 : 1) as eluent, 5 was eluded first (72 mg, 34%), m.p. $201-03^\circ$ (Found : C, 46.82; H, 2.01; N, 34.09. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{ClN}_5$ (205.6) calcd. for : C, 46.70; H, 1.96; N, 34.06%); δ (DMSO-d_6)⁴ 7.27 (1H, dd, J_{ab} 4.4, J_{bc} 8.2 Hz, H_b), 9.03 (1H, dd, J_{ac} 1.8, J_{bc} 8.2 Hz, H_c), 9.06 (1H, s, H_d) and 9.23 (1H, dd, J_{ab} 4.4, J_{ac} 1.8 Hz, H_a); m/z 205 (M^+). Compound 6 was eluded next, (110 mg, 52%), m.p. $254-56^\circ$ (Found : C, 46.77; H, 1.80; N, 34.11. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{ClN}_5$ (205.6) calcd. for : C, 46.70; H, 1.96; N, 34.06%); δ (DMSO-d_6)⁴ 8.07 (1H, dd, J_{ab} 4.4, J_{bc} 8.3 Hz, H_b), 8.73 (1H, dd, J_{ac} 1.6, J_{bc} 8.3 Hz, H_c), 9.33 (1H, dd, J_{ab} 4.4, J_{ac} 1.6 Hz, H_a) and 9.70 (1H, s, H_d); m/z 205 (M^+).

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4. 250 MHz: PTF-WM spectrometer. Elemental analysis and all spectral data were recorded at the Institute of Organic Chemistry, Regensburg, West Germany.